

SIGNIFICANCE OF INTENSIVE METHOD AND ITS BASIC FEATURES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article is about an intensive teaching method that is useful and essential one in education to conduct the lessons in appropriate way. Much has been done and is being done in our country and abroad to intensify foreign language teaching. This has led to the development of new intensive methods. So what is an intensive method? How can it be understood? Intensive teaching is the process of teaching students to speak in a foreign language in a short period of time. This is based on the students' internal psychological capacity and memory. Thus, the intensive method (or intensive) teaching has the following two characteristics: Organize a certain amount of educational material in a short period of time and carry out the corresponding foreign language speaking activity; Maximizing the use of all the resources (psychological capabilities) of personal memory, ie increasing the activity of students.

In recent years, much needs to be done to increase student engagement in the classroom. One of the most important tasks is to create an environment of verbal communication in order to increase the activity of students in the classroom, using the internal capabilities of personal memory. The methods used by the teacher and the various visual aids should be aimed at this goal. The psychological state of verbal communication is one of the most important tasks in increasing the activity of students. E.I.Passov, one of the well-known

Methodist scholars, says that the communicative approach used in modern foreign language teaching is a form of intensive teaching based on speech situations.

The intensive method was first developed in the early twentieth century on the basis of the "correct" method. Prof. According to E. I. Gez, "The right method has created a favorable environment and basis for intensive foreign language teaching." Some of the key aspects of the right method, such as interest in oral

discourse, especially the choice of speech situations for dialogic speech, and the need to increase student engagement in the classroom, are the basis of some modern intensive methods. This is natural, because each new method retains the advantages of the previous method.

In recent years, words denoting a new direction, such as audiolingual, audiovisual, hypnopedia, relaxation, suggestopedia, rhythmopedia, have become more common in the methodological literature. It should be noted that audiolingual and audiovisual methods cannot be used in intensive training. This is hampered by their principled nature of not relying on the use of the mother tongue, the abundance of learning, memorization and creative exercises by imitating the language. Hypnopedics, Relaxed Therapy - these methods only give good results in memorizing language material, but do not provide use in speech. That is why the well-known scientist prof. Gegechkori L.Sh. suggests that hypnopedia and relaxation should be considered as techniques that can be used in foreign language teaching because they are intended only to remember the information being conveyed. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the integration of research in pedagogy, psychology, social psychology, and medical sciences in the study of the individual as an object and the identification of all its creative potential. An important issue today is the focus on students' new thinking, creative thinking, and preparing them for life. This increases the need for a comprehensive study of the individual. Thus, the student's personality has become a central figure in the learning

process. G. Lozanov - psychotherapist, doctor of medical sciences, Bulgarian scientist - focused on the study of human internal reserves. He began to study three important factors: 1. Opening memory reserves; 2. To study the intellectual activity of the student; 3. Positive emotion, (loses the feeling of fatigue). The role, authority of the teacher; the relationship between teacher and student; mutual trust, a high level of motivation, the opening of the individual's internal reserve capacity. (This thesis is explained).

Lozanov's method admits that it includes:

- 1) in the study of a large number of speech units;
- 2) to develop students' ability to use language, vocabulary in the process of speaking a foreign language, to use the learned unit of speech in another situation;
- 3) creating high motivation to learn to read;
- 4) the presence of psychological barriers (shyness, fear, humanity) gives very good results in removing.

It is noteworthy that Lozanov did not set himself the task of developing a method of teaching a foreign language. In the 60s and 70s, Lozanov's method was used in foreign language learning. At present, scientists and methodologists have developed their own way of combining intensive methods with the "Right-Practical" method used in our country. He said that it is expedient to apply only some principles of this method (Lozanov).

1. Emotional-smislovoy method (I. Yu. Shexter) to focus on meaningful change in the process of role-playing games. This view is based on the idea that a person's personal thinking does not come from a set of language units of any kind. The main tool

in this method is in the system of communicative tasks.

This method of training is divided into 3 forms (periods):

a) Learn to speak based on the most common situations in life. No grammar, no homework. By the end of this period, you will be able to read textbooks containing 1200-1400 lexical units.

b) Transition to a professional speech process. Monological speech is widely developed in all respects. Gradually, refereeing begins with the study of writing and grammar. Teaching a foreign language on the basis of various games, consisting of problematic situations related to the profession, using texts of a scientific and political nature.

c) Speech is increasingly shaped by a particular profession. Special texts, work documents, professional correspondence form the material of study.

2. The intensive course offered by L Gegechkori is designed for adults. There are 3 periods. The inter-period stage (ie the stage of language preparation) is the main feature that distinguishes this method from other methods. In this case, the language material is consciously assimilated.

3. An experiment was conducted at the Petrograd Forestry Academy on the intensive method of teaching foreign languages to students. The learning process is organized as follows:

1st semester - speech preparation exercises based on conscious learning of a foreign language;

2nd semester - Development of dialogic speech based on the method of G. Lozanov;

Semester 3 - teaching a wide range of profiles based on conscious study of language material;

4th semester - development of monologue speech based on the method of G. Lozanov;
5th semester - study of texts on the specialty;

4. The Sleeping Course (Plesnevich A. S. tried English teaching) is designed for 10 days. Objective: To provide researchers with scientific and professional contacts with foreign colleagues. This method can be used in the final stages of teaching students. As a review of previous topics.

5. Suggestokibernetic integral method. (Petrusinsky V.V.) (for adults) Cybernetization of suggestive control is the basis of this method. Training is provided by automated technical means. The teacher is not present. It only controls the selection of materials and the knowledge, skills and abilities. This method mainly helps to automate the initial method and chooses to memorize the lexical material.

In conclusion, some features of this or that intensive course can be applied in the process of teaching in a foreign language higher education system. It is designed to make a person more active in the learning process. The term "method" is widely used as a general theory of educational teaching. Didactics interprets the term "method" in terms of the way teachers and students work to gain knowledge, skills, attitudes, and opportunities for teachers. General teaching methods have been developed for the subjects that teach the basics of science. The methodology of teaching a foreign language is developed in the methodology, taking into account the specifics of the subject. The use of methods in foreign language teaching has a long history. In foreign language teaching methods, the term "method" has three main meanings.

First, a whole line in the history of methodology (translation method, correct method, comparative method, mixed method);

Second, the training system that is part of the above;

Third, the way teachers and students interact.

In the history of foreign language teaching, the first and second methods are called "historical" methods, and the third is called "process expression". Historically, the methods have been grouped into four groups, with the addition of the words "translation", "correct", "comparative", "mixed" to their names. All the methods in the centuries-old history of the unit are grouped into four categories. A brief analysis of each of them is required, because in the first method, some of their features are used in a certain way.

The method of intensive learning of foreign languages was originally created for the conditions of coursework. Experimental work has shown that the intensive method can be used when working with all age groups. However, the senior stage of education provides the most opportunities. The reasons for this are: the greatest degree of personality formation, an extensive information stock, the desire for knowledge of the world through communication with other people, the presence of the original language base.

The basis of the intensive teaching methods is the suggestopedic method. In the 60s in Sofia, an absolutely unique method for learning foreign languages was developed by the Bulgarian psychotherapist Georgi Lozanov at the Institute of Specialization and Advanced

Medical Studies (ISUL). The main goal of the method was, using means of suggestive influence, to remove the complexes and barriers of people learning a foreign language and further, introducing them into a state of physical relaxation and mental concentration, to achieve the effect of hypermnesia (that is, over-memorization). In the course of the experiment G. Lozanov managed to ensure that 1000 words in French were learned in one day. According to the scientist, people use from 5 to 10% of the capacity of the brain, and using its method, these figures could increase by 3 -5 times, compared to traditional teaching methods. This form of suggestion was called "suggestopedia" (from Latin *suggestio* suggestion, hint Greek *paideia* training), i.e. the use of methods of suggestion in learning.

G. Lozanov identifies three types of suggestion, which are used in the educational process to remove all kinds of psychological barriers among students. The teacher conducts classes based on the psychological factors of emotional impact, using logical forms of presentation of the material. In the classroom, there are special techniques that activate learning. The teacher uses in the classroom various types of art (music, painting, theater elements) for the purpose of emotional impact on the student and harmonization of the lesson.

The main provisions of suggestopedia are as follows:

- 1) the training should be joyful and relaxed;
- 2) it should be carried out on both conscious and subconscious levels;

3) in training, it is necessary to use usually untapped reserves of consciousness in order to increase effectiveness.

In conclusion, it has long been recognized that intensive methods of language teaching rank second best only to actual residence in the country where the studied language is native. These methods are successful because the structure of each language is intensively studied as an indigenous integer to its own individual pattern. Overcoming the barrier felt by many students through unfamiliarity with the new language and their reluctance to abandon the area of the familiar are difficulties which the instructor must, first of all, strive to overcome. Added to these, is the students' anticipated fear of ridicule should they quite unconsciously make blunders. Intensive methods of instruction in which class and lecture sessions are

stretched far beyond the conventional 3 to 4 one-hour weekly periods aim to produce a comfortable familiarity, or "submergence" in the language: a condition however, rarely achieved in a half-year of usual instruction or even during an entire year.

So, intensive methods have contributed considerable energy to the method of teaching foreign languages in general. Achievements of intensive methods in the field of activating the processes of perception and assimilation of the material basis of communication, in opening up its reserves of motivation and in developing adequate forms of collective interaction should as soon as possible become the property of teaching methods at the university, to increase its effectiveness and efficiency.

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